

Influence of Personality Styles and Emotional Intelligence on Academic Stress among University Students

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Academic stress is a growing concern among university students, often linked to both personal and emotional factors. This study investigates the relationship between academic stress, personality styles, and emotional intelligence among university students, and further explores the predictive impact of personality traits and emotional intelligence on academic stress. The sample comprised 802 university students (362 males & 440 females) selected through a multistage sampling technique from various universities in the Bathinda district of Punjab. Findings revealed that there is a significant correlation between neuroticism and openness personality traits with academic stress. Also, self-emotional appraisal, a domain of emotional intelligence showed correlation with academic stress. Multiple linear regression also revealed the impact of neuroticism, openness, and emotional intelligence on academic stress. Hence, this study provides an insight into how individual differences impact the level of experienced academic stress, paving the way for the development of personalized counselling strategies.

Keywords: Academic stress, emotional intelligence, personality traits, university students

The university students are exposed to different kinds of distress, and one of such distress, which is very common in the literature as well as in the real case scenario, is 'Academic Stress' (Barbayannis et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2024; Deng et al., 2022). As a consequence, the mental health of university students is on the brink. In India, particularly, there were 13,089 suicides in 2021 as reported by the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) (Maji et al., 2024). Suicide rates have increased by 70% among university students (2011-2012) and these are expected to be 6-8 times more than being reported due to underreported suicide-reports (Gupta & Basera, 2021; Maji et al., 2024).

Stress is a complex concept; it varies from missing the bus to the loss of someone close. It is biological, cognitive and psychological and has behavioral, cognitive and psychological consequences (Dorsey et al., 2022). Stress is elicited from 'stressor', a stimulus capable of producing-stress (Chu et al., 2019). Similarly, academic stress arises from various factors such as exams, a robust syllabus, parental expectations and competition (Barbayannis et al., 2022). As dreadful as 'academic stress' sounds, there are various internal (personality traits, emotional intelligence, coping styles) (Young et

al., 2019) and external factors (social support) which acts as a buffer against it. In the present study, the main focus is on two internal factors which help an individual to cope with stress, personality and emotional intelligence (EI).

Personality has been studied widely in academic settings in terms of Big Five Model (OCEAN) (McCrae & Costa, 1987). In this model, the five dimensions are Openness (flexible, adventurous, open to novel experiences), Conscientiousness (responsible & disciplined), Extraversion (social & active), Agreeableness (warm & cooperative), and Neuroticism (tension, worry & over-thinking) (McCrae & Costa, 1987). Conscientiousness and extraversion act as a buffer against stress; however, neuroticism makes an individual prone to stress, emotionally. That is where emotional intelligence (EI) comes into the picture as a buffer to stress (Merhi et al., 2018). EI is basically perceiving, understanding, and managing emotions to use them to facilitate the thoughts (Mayer & Salovey, 1997). People with high EI are self-aware about their emotions and elicit socially accurate emotions by managing their anxiety, stress, and any other negative emotions (Merhi et al., 2018). In the literature, it has been well established that EI is a significant predictor of success (Merhi et al., 2018) more than general intelligence and it can undo the adverse effect of academic stress.

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We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.
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Academic Stress in University Students

With increasing suicide rates among students all over the world, academic stress has become a concern. There has been a condition of burnout in university students due to prolonged academic stress, which ultimately leads to decreased cognitive ability, poor academic performance, decreased life satisfaction, sleep disturbances, decreased well-being, suicidal ideation, anxiety and depression (Barbayannis et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2024; Deng et al., 2022; Young et al., 2019). These fatal consequences of academic stress on students' health highlight-the urgent need to address the major sources of academic stress and also to determine the individual differences that enable them to cope with academic stress and the ability to manage the academic demands effectively.

Review of Literature

A detailed and comprehensive literature review was undertaken to

illustrate the existing studies done on academic stress, personality styles, and EI among university students. The present section gives an overview of theoretical frameworks and empirical findings to establish a foundation for the present study.

A study conducted by García-Martínez et al. (2022) on 1022 students illustrates a protective role of EI against stress, showcasing a negative relationship between EI and stress, anxiety, and depression. Moreover, neuroticism showed a significant relationship with academic stress.

Abdelrahman et al. (2025) conducted a study in Mediterranean countries among university students. The result showed the negative association between EI and academic stress. They pointed out that students with high EI manage the academic stress effectively, maintain-motivation and seek the social support whenever needed.

Khorasani et al. (2023) undertook a descriptive and quasi-experimental study to explore the effect of EI on stress levels among 200 students. The findings illustrate that EI and stress have a negative correlation and with enhanced EI skills, the academic stress can be decreased, controlled, and managed.

Another study, examining the relationship of emotional indulgence and academic stress among undergraduate University student ($n=119$) between the age group of 18 to 24 from different colleges of Kerala conducted by Roy et al. (2021). The result showed a significant relationship between EI and academic stress.

Ibrahim and Elhabashy (2025) conducted a correlational study on 654 students and concluded that personality traits such as agreeableness and conscientiousness are negatively linked to academic stress, while neuroticism has a positive relationship with academic stress.

Another study conducted by Mohamed et al. (2025) using cross-sectional descriptive survey. The result shows that higher levels of EI were positively associated with better stress management and an increased level of resilience. Using structural equation modelling, it was found that EI significantly impacts students' ability to cope with academic challenges.

Saklofske et al. (2011) studied the association between personality, EI, and coping styles in a group of university students at University of Edinburgh. The stress showed a significant relationship with personality, affect and emotion regulation factors. The factor such as agreeableness and conscientiousness was found to be significant.

Ghiabi and Besharat (2011) conducted the correlation analysis to assess the relationship between personality dimensions and EI in a sample of university students from Tehran. The result signifies that EI was positively predicted by extroversion and negatively by neuroticism, respectively. In another study conducted by Grehan et al. (2011) on university students revealed that out of five dimensions, only conscientiousness was significantly correlated with EI.

Othman et al. (2016) conducted the study to explore the relationship between EI and personality traits among pharmacy students of Malaysia during the stressful academic environment. The result shows that neuroticism affects the psychological health, the most during any stressful period, while other factors such as emotional control, emotional conscientiousness and extraversion were also associated with depression, stress, and anxiety.

Relevance of the Study

Academic stress is becoming a major psychological concern among university students affecting their mental health and overall general

well-being. Numerous studies have shown the protective role of personality styles and EI. Personality styles ascertain how an individual will perceive the academic pursuits and challenges and EI will make sure to cope and manage the academic stress effectively. For instance, a student high in EI, conscientiousness or extraversion will employ an adaptive coping strategy and showcase a high psychological resilience. However, despite the preventive role of EI and personality styles, there are few investigations in the Indian context which examines these two variables together as the predictors of academic stress. Therefore, the present study examines the impact of personality traits and EI on academic stress of university students.

Objectives of the Study

- To assess the academic stress, personality style, and emotional intelligence in university students.
- To examine the relationship between academic stress, personality style, and emotional intelligence.
- To examine impact of personality styles and emotional intelligence on academic stress.

Method

Participants

The study population consisted of 802 university students (362 males & 440 females) between the age group of 18-26 years (Mean age = 22 years). Multistage random sampling technique was employed to select the sample from the Bathinda district of Punjab. Only sample who were enrolled in the social sciences or basic sciences academic disciplines were recruited for the present study. Further, this study has excluded the participants who were not willing to participate or belonged to other academic disciplines. The table below shows the socio-demographic profile of the subjects.

Table 1
Socio-demographic Profile of University Students

Variable	Category	N	%
Gender	Male	362	45.1
	Female	440	54.9
Age	18-20	113	14.1
	21-23	464	57.9
	24-26	225	28.1
		Mean=22.3	SD=1.91
Academic Discipline	Social Science	380	47.4
	Basic Science	422	52.6
University	Central University of Punjab	602	75
	Guru Kashi University	200	25
Education	UG	144	18
	PG	658	82
Accommodation	Hosteller	435	54.2
	Day Scholar	367	45.8
Community	ST	44	5.5
	SC	245	30.5
	OBC	264	32.9
	UR	220	27.4
Migration	Minority	29	3.6
	Migrated	505	63
Area of living	Non-Migrated	297	37
	Rural	460	57.4
	Urban	342	42.6

Birth order	1st	270	33.8
	2nd	291	36.4
	3rd	166	20.8
	4th	62	7.8
	5th	11	1.4
Family Income	No Mention	28	3.5
	1000 to 20000	258	32.3
	21000 to 40000	202	25.3
	41000 to 60000	133	16.6
	61000 to 80000	96	12.0
	80000 to 100000	83	10.4
Family Environment	Peaceful	618	77.1
Family Environment	Not so peaceful	137	17.1
	Disturbed	38	4.7
	Very much disturbed	9	1.1

Research Design

The present study is a quantitative-correlational research-design which examines the relationship and predictive influence of personality and EI on academic stress among university students.

Measures

Socio-Demographic Information: A basic information schedule was prepared to collect all the necessary demographic information from the participants. Data includes information on gender, age, academic discipline, education, area of living, migration, family income, and family environment.

Academic Stress Scale: The Academic Stress Scale by Rajendran and Kaliappan (1990) was administered to assess the participants' academic stress. It is a self-report scale of 40 items, divided into five different areas that measure personal inadequacy, fear of failure, interpersonal difficulties, teacher-student relationship, and academic workload. It employs a five-point Likert-type format, ranging from 'no stress' (0) to 'extreme stress' (4), and higher scores indicate greater levels of academic stress. It has good internal consistency with Cronbach's alpha values above 0.70 and test-retest reliability, along with content and construct validity.

Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS): The Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS; Wong, Song, & Law, 2002) was administered to see the emotional intelligence. The scale consisted of four domains: Self-emotional appraisal, Regulation of emotion, others' emotional appraisal, and use of emotion. It is a self-report instrument designed to assess EI through 16 items grouped into four dimensions. Participants responded on a 7-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 7 (*strongly agree*), with higher scores reflecting greater levels of EI. The scale demonstrates strong internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha values ranging from .83 to .90 across the four dimensions. Furthermore, WLEIS has demonstrated good convergent validity with other EI measures, such as the EQ-i and the Trait Meta-Mood Scale.

NEO Five-Factor Inventory: Lastly, participants' personality traits were measured using the NEO Five-Factor Inventory (Costa & McCrae, 1992). It is a 60-item self-report instrument designed to assess the five major personality domains (neuroticism, extraversion, openness to experience, agreeableness, and conscientiousness). Participants respond using a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (*Strongly Disagree*) to 5 (*Strongly Agree*). The instrument demonstrates internal consistency reliability, with coefficients reported as 0.83 for conscientiousness and 0.80 for neuroticism. The subscales for agreeableness and Extraversion showed reliability coefficients of 0.60 and 0.58, respectively.

Data Analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS v27. To find the variability in the sample, descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, and mean were used. The inferential statistics were used to test the hypothesis. To establish the relationship between personality traits, emotional intelligence, and academic stress, a correlation analysis was applied. Further, multiple regression was employed to determine whether the correlated variables predict academic stress in young adults.

Results

Table 2

Correlation between Academic stress, dimensions of Personality, and dimensions of Emotional Intelligence

Variables	AS	N	E	O	A	C	TEI	ROE	SEA	UOE	OEA
AS	1										
N	.116**	1									
E	-.001	.077**	1								
O	.095**	.038	-.038	1							
A	.012	-.079*	-.054	.150*	1						
C	-.051	-.002	.103**	.031	.182**	1					
TEI	-.047	.017	.082*	.053	.033	.168**	1				
ROE	-.023	.011	.105**	.075**	.072*	.148**	.751**	1			
SEA	-.101**	.051	.079*	.042	.039	.173**	.761**	.542**	1		
UOE	-.032	-.002	.033	.039	.009	.145**	.755**	.497**	.499**	1	
OEA	-.036	-.052	.051	.074*	-.011	.060	.712**	.401**	.441**	.459*	1

Note. ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$, AS= academic stress, N= neuroticism, E= extroversion, O= openness, C= conscientiousness, TEI= total emotional intelligence, ROE= regulation of emotion, SEA= self-emotional appraisal, UOE= use of emotion, OEA= other's emotional appraisal

Table 3
Multiple Regression Predicting Academic Stress from Personality Traits

Predictors	B	SEB	Beta	Lower Bond	Upper Bond	t	p
Constant	23.847	6.473		11.141	36.554	3.684	<.001
Neuroticism	.579	.180	.112	.225	.933	3.208	.001
Openness	.488	.188	.091	.119	.857	2.594	.010

Note. $R^2 = .022$, Adjusted $R^2 = .019$, $F(2,799) = 8.837$, $p < .001$, B= unstandardized regression coefficient, SE B= standard error, β = standardized coefficient

The result indicated that neuroticism ($r = .116$) and openness ($r = .095$) dimensions of personality significantly correlated with academic stress. Additionally, the self-emotional appraisal dimension of personality was found to negatively correlated with academic stress ($r = -0.101$). Extraversion dimension of personality was found to be positively correlated with TOE ($r = .082$), and the dimensions of EI like ROE ($r = .105$), and SEA ($r = .079$). Similarly, the openness dimension of personality was found to be positively correlated with the EI dimension; ROE ($r = .075$), and OEA ($r = .074$). Moreover, agreeableness dimension of personality was found to be correlated with ROE ($r = .072$).

A multiple regression analysis was conducted to examine the impact of personality traits on academic stress among university students. The overall model was significant, $F(2,799) = 8.837$, $p < .001$, and accounted for approximately 2.2% of the variance in academic stress ($R^2 = .022$, Adjusted $R^2 = .019$). Neuroticism ($\beta = .112$, $p = .001$), and openness ($\beta = .091$, $p = .010$) contributed to predicting academic stress.

A multiple regression analysis was conducted to investigate the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic stress among university students. The overall model was not significant, $F(5,796) = 2.184$, $p = .054$, and accounted for approximately 1.4% of the variance in academic stress ($R^2 = .014$, Adjusted $R^2 = .007$). Among all the dimensions of EI, only SEA ($\beta = -.887$, $p = .003$) contributed to predict academic stress.

Graph 1

The Normal P-P Plot of Standardised Residuals Indicated that the Residuals Followed a Near-normal Distribution

Table 4
Multiple Regression Predicting Academic stress from Emotional Intelligence

Predictors	B	SEB	Beta	Lower Bond	Upper Bond	t	p
Constant	58.582	5.245		48.285	68.878	11.168	<.001
TEI	.241	.198	.149	-.148	.631	1.217	.224
ROE	-.027	.311	-.005	-.637	.582	-.087	.931
SEA	-.887	.298	-.174	-1.471	-.302	-2.976	.003
UOE	-.179	.313	-.033	-.794	.435	-.573	.567
OEA	-.247	.287	-.049	-.811	.317	-.860	.390

Note. $R^2 = .014$, Adjusted $R^2 = .007$, $F(5,796) = 2.184$, $p = .054$, B= unstandardized regression coefficient, SE B= standard error, β = standardized coefficient, TEI= total emotional intelligence, ROE= regulation of emotion, SEA= self-emotional appraisal, UOE= use of emotion, OEA= other's emotional appraisal

Graph 2

The Normal P-P Plot of Standardised Residuals Indicated that the Residuals Followed a Near-normal Distribution

Discussion

The present study sought to provide insight into how personal disposition impacts academic stress. The study aimed to examine the correlation and impact of different personality traits on the academic stress experienced by university students. Further, it also attempted to explore the correlation and impact of EI on academic stress.

Personality Traits and Academic Stress

The current study found a correlation between academic stress and neuroticism. It also shows a positive and significant impact of neuroticism on academic stress. Neuroticism is characterized by feelings of despair, panic in stressful situations, and a tendency towards negative emotions (Munjirin et al., 2023). Hence, the students with high neuroticism have a higher risk of negative emotions, emotional instability, and poor coping, which also leads to more psychological distress, resulting in higher academic stress (Yusoff et al., 2021; Schneider et al., 2011). The emotional instability further affects memory, attention, and self-efficacy (Ainie et al.,

2023) and impacts academic stress. Additionally, openness also correlates with and has an impact on academic stress. Students with an open mindset generally exhibit lower academic stress and possess better coping mechanisms, possibly due to a more flexible and creative approach to problem-solving, which in turn leads to lower academic stress (Schneider et al., 2011). Héctor Galindo-Dominguez et al. (2021) noted that people with low openness tend to experience more distress, while those with high openness can better manage academic challenges. Chiappelli et al. (2021) even found that stressful life events were significantly associated with openness, suggesting a complex interplay between personality and stress experiences.

EI and Academic Stress

Academic stress has also been shown to have a positive correlation with self-emotional appraisal (SEA). According to Lazarus and Folkman's (1984), cognitive appraisal theory, students who can better evaluate their emotions accurately in academic work and challenges may experience lower academic stress. Students who have a high Self-Emotional Appraisal (SEA) can accurately recognize, interpret, and regulate negative feelings, which helps them fulfil academic demands more effectively (Peña-Sarrionandia et al., 2015) possibly leading to lower academic stress. Most studies report a negative correlation between EI and academic stress: students with higher EI tend to experience less academic stress, as they are better equipped to manage emotions and adapt to challenges (Iskandar & Rasidin, 2024; Roy et al., 2021).

Personality and EI

Additionally, the present study found Total Emotional Intelligence (TEI) and the dimensions of EI, such as Regulation of Emotion (ROE), and Self-Emotional Appraisal (SEA), to be significantly and positively associated with the Extraversion domain of personality. According to the Big Five Personality Theory (Costa & McCrae, 1985), and Trait Emotional Intelligence Theory (Petrides & Furnham, 2001) extraversion is linked with emotional expressiveness and adaptive emotional functioning. This suggests that students with high extraversion tend to experience more interaction and employ adaptive coping strategies, such as seeking social support and engaging in social activities, which in turn strengthen their emotional understanding and confidence. Thus, students who are extroverted exhibit higher EI due to their emotionally expressive nature and are more socially engaged, making them more comfortable navigating their emotions (Siegling, Furnham, & Petrides, 2015). They are more effective at interpersonal emotion regulation (ROE), likely due to their social dominance, positive affect, and preference for proactive strategies like cognitive reappraisal (Wickett et al., 2023). SEA is higher in extraverts because they engage in emotional expression and reflection through communication, which shows a stronger ability to identify and understand their own emotions (Kafetsios & Zampetakis, 2008).

The present study also found a positive relationship between the conscientiousness domain of personality and EI (TEI) and the dimensions of EI, including Regulation of Emotion (ROE), Use of Emotion (UAE), and Self-emotional Appraisal (SEA). According to Big Five personality theory (Costa & McCrae, 1992) conscientiousness reflects self-discipline and strong regulation. These characteristics enhance an individual's ability to understand

their emotional (SEA) response (ROE) and use emotion to guide goal-directed behavior (UOE) (McCrae & Costa, 1999; Roberts, Jackson, Fayard, Edmonds, & Meints, 2009). This indicates that conscientious students are typically organized, disciplined, goal-oriented, and self-motivated. These characteristics contribute to higher trait EI because conscientious people are more responsible and intentional in understanding themselves and others. Petrides et al. (2016) found that individuals with strong self-control and planning abilities tend to exhibit better emotional regulation, as they are more effective at handling emotional situations (Gross & John, 2003). Conscientiousness is further linked to the better use of emotion (UOE) because individuals with high conscientiousness tend to focus primarily on their emotions when achieving goals, maintaining motivation, and solving problems (McCrae & Costa, 1999). Conscientious individuals tend to engage in self-monitoring and reflection, which supports higher Self-Emotional Appraisal (SEA), enabling them to accurately identify and evaluate their emotional states (Schutte et al., 1998; Salovey & Mayer, 1990).

Conclusion

Our findings contribute to the understanding of psychological intrapersonal attributes among university students. The study showed how psychological factors help to mitigate students' academic stress. The study explored how the Big Five personality traits and dimensions of EI impact academic stress among university students. Neuroticism and Openness have shown impact on academic stress, whereas the Self-Emotional Appraisal (SEA) domain of EI acts as a negative and significant predictor of academic stress. Additionally, extraversion and conscientiousness showed a positive and significant relationship with the domains of EI. Overall, personality traits and EI are significantly connected to the experience of academic stress. Hence, the findings of this study will facilitate the formulation of personalized counselling strategies in universities, thereby enhancing student support based on their personality profiles and emotional intelligence competencies.

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Received November 5, 2025

Revision received November 18, 2025

Accepted November 23, 2025